

Extreme heat in cities

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With societies becoming more urbanised, many cities are experiencing what is known as the **Urban Heat Island (UHI)** effect.

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This is a phenomenon where urban areas experience significantly higher temperatures compared to their rural surroundings.

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This difference is primarily due to human activities and the characteristics of urban environments such as materials and structures that absorb heat, waste heat from vehicles, and reduced green spaces.

The combination of more frequent and prolonged heat waves, coupled with the UHI effect, has a profound impact on society, particularly affecting the most vulnerable and posing challenges for local and regional health and energy sectors.

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In **CLIM4cities**, we set out to address the need for a low-cost, efficient and scalable Urban Climate prediction system for effective planning, response, adaptation measures, assessment and anticipation of extreme heat events in urban areas.

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